

Pedagogical model of improving physical education teachers' professional competence

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Abstract. The modernization of physical education content provokes its refocusing not only on the subject competences, but also metasubject, personal, social, communicative, gnostic, projecting, informational and others competences. This contributes the increase in requirements to the system of professional development of physical education teachers who need to successfully meet the educational objectives, showing the completeness and effectiveness of their personal and professional characteristics, the activity of pedagogical thinking and possession of an integrated system of professional skills with a high level of professional competence. Organizational and pedagogical predictive model of the educational process serves as a condition for constructing the educational space initiating the improvement and self-improvement of physical education teachers' professional competence in the process of professional development. Creating the motivational space, initiating individual work of students and assisting them in developing their individual trajectory of selfimprovement were the basis of the developed model.

Keywords: professional competence of physical education teachers, organizational and pedagogical predictive model, the components of activity, the diagnostic tool.

In the context of modernization of Uzbek education, there is an increasing need for teachers who are able to take a personal and humane position, organize the educational process based on modern educational paradigms, and educate a person of culture. We are talking about the cultural aspect of the content of education, which consists in the development of the individual in all spheres of his activity through mastering the achievements of world and domestic culture, mastering the system of knowledge about nature, society and man. In this context, the process of development of society and personality cannot be complete without the progress of physical culture. This type of activity promotes the spiritual and physical development of a person and forms values that have general cultural significance. Improving educational paradigms leads to a change in the status of physical education as a humanitarian educational subject. This necessitates updating the content of physical education education and thereby significantly changes the view on the quality of a teacher's professional and personal positions, requiring a rethinking and restructuring of the nature of his professional activity. The physical education teacher becomes the bearer of the updated content of education, the organizer of pedagogical conditions that ensure the effectiveness of activities. In this regard, among the pressing problems of modern additional professional education, the problem of its modernization comes to the fore by strengthening the humanistic contexts of the pedagogical activity of a specialist in physical culture and sports, who is called upon to build his individual pedagogical activity on value-semantic foundations, i.e. to have professional -personal competence. At the same time, no more than 20% of physical education teachers rely on the idea of democratization and humanization, 5–10% implement an activity-based approach, and up to 10% of teachers use psychological-pedagogical and psychological-physiological theories. New approaches to assessing student performance, focused on quality criteria, carry out from 10 to 20%, use a variety of creative methods and forms of teaching, with an emphasis on motivation of classes, up to 20% of teachers, use computers and other new technical teaching aids in classes no more 5% of teachers [1]. Until recently, in the

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system of advanced training of physical education specialists, there was a training model that reflected the realities of the traditional educational paradigm of higher professional physical education. Innovative directions associated with updating the professional education of specialists in the field of physical culture and sports on a humanistic, value-semantic, personality-oriented basis are reflected in the works of a number of authors (I. P. Andriadi, V. K. Balsevich, S. N. Begidova, V. V. Belyaeva, M. Ya. Vilensky, Z. N. Vyatkina, V. D. Gorbatov, Yu. D. Zheleznyak, A. F. Kulikov, L. M. Kustov, A. V. Lotonenko, L. I. Lubysheva, V. A. Magin, A. Ya. Nain, R. A. Piloyan, G. N. Ponomarev, F. I. Sobyenin, G. M. Solovyov, etc.). Recently, many studies have appeared devoted to the problem of improving the qualifications of specialists in physical culture and sports in the context of updating the content of education (V. U. Ageevets, E. R. Akhmedzyanov, A. N. Bleer, O. B. Dmitriev, S. P. Evseev, Yu. A. Kashirtsev, N. N. Kiseleva, etc.). At the same time, research related to the search and development of professional development systems based on humanistic foundations and aimed at improving the professional competence of physical education teachers, in our opinion, is still insufficient. Among the many contradictions, we highlight one related to the increased need of modern schools for a professionally competent personality of a physical education teacher and the insufficient development of pedagogical models for organizing the process of advanced training, built on competence-based, activity-based principles. A study devoted to the theoretical justification and development of a model for advanced training aimed at improving the professional competence of physical education teachers was carried out from 2001 to 2006 on the basis of the Rostov Regional Institute for Advanced Training and Retraining of Education Workers. 527 physical education teachers of secondary schools in the Rostov region took part in the testing. Solving one of the research tasks, we examined the essence of modeling, which scientists call the leading category of the theory of knowledge, as well as a method of scientific research [2], which has two aspects: theoretically and experimentally. In general, a model is considered in science as a system of elements and objects that reproduces certain aspects, connections, and functions of the subject of research [2]. The model development strategy can be represented as a system of step-by-step action-elements: – analytical understanding of the content, facts and factors of the functioning of the educational system; – identification of contradictions that make it difficult to achieve a high-quality result in the system of advanced training; – selection of methodological foundations for the model; – building a system of goals for improving the professional competence of physical education teachers in the process of advanced training; – building a holistic educational space for a professional development system that initiates the improvement of professional competence of physical education teachers; – determination of criteria and levels of professional competence of physical education teachers. Developing the logic of the above, we chose the following as a methodological basis: – provisions on the integrity of the pedagogical process, considered in a sequence of interrelated stages (N. G. Abramova, I. Ya. Lerner, M. N. Skatkin, etc.); – provisions on a systematic approach to organizing learning processes in the context of its integrity (V. G. Afanasyev, G. I. Gerasimov, A. Ya. Danilyuk, V. S. Ilyin, etc.); – the theory of the gradual formation of mental actions (P. Ya. Galperin, N. F. Talyzina), which assumes the need to create conditions that ensure a certain system of actions for students, in the context of the commonality of internal and external human activity; – provisions on pedagogical synergetics, which involves changing the mode of operation of students' consciousness and transferring it from the mode of reflection to the mode of creative production of personal meanings and experience, which allows

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us to perceive the professional image as a living, complexly organized integrity (S. V. Kulnevich, R. A. Kurenkova) ; – the concept of personality-oriented education, aimed at initiating the subjective properties and potentials of students, as well as at developing their personal universal functions in the mode of integration of procedural and psychological interaction plans (E. V. Bondarevskaya, V. V. Serikov, I. S. Yakimanskaya and etc.). Thus, the problem was determined - to organize a holistic pedagogical process of improving the professional competence of physical education teachers. At the same time, we followed the provisions developed by V. S. Ilyin about the holistic properties of the process and its influence not only on individual functions and properties of the individual, but also on the individual as a whole [3]. When developing a pedagogical model for organizing the process of improving the professional competence of physical education teachers on a competency-based basis, we chose the system of personality-oriented components of professional pedagogical education proposed by M. M. Levina as the substantive basis for design [4].

1. Personal-motivational component, which presupposes the motivation of educational activities: the formation of personal meaning of educational and professional activities; development of professional orientation of the individual, personal and professional self-determination and self-realization; development of self-organization in educational activities and self-regulation of behavior; development of self-assessment of one's professional readiness.

2. Personal-activity (communicative component), which involves the development of the personality of the subject of activity: the implementation of the value-target function of humanistic training through personal orientation of learning; development and formation of independence, arbitrariness of actions, selectivity of educational actions based on personal meaning formation and awareness of the value of the teaching profession; mastering contact methods of regulating the educational activities of students; systematic application of personally oriented learning technologies; the use of individualized methods of pedagogical communication based on a focus on the age, typological and personal characteristics of the individual; pedagogical communication based on the general patterns of interpersonal and professional pedagogical communication for the purpose of informational substantive influence and psychological regulation of educational activities.

3. Cognitive-creative (cultural) component, which involves the implementation of a cultural approach: the formation of a scientific worldview based on the systematic nature of scientific knowledge and professional practice; subordination of the subjectively perceived target function of the educational process with the value-target function of advanced training; understanding educational goals in terms of developing personal and professional self-determination; students' mastery of areas of subject-specific professional and psychological-pedagogical education; students' awareness of the importance of personal information readiness for professional activities, free selectivity of professional actions, improvement of professional knowledge and skills; development of professional systematic thinking, flexibility, criticality, creative activity, development of creative individuality; formation of professional reflexivity and self-correction; the formation of self-organization based on the motivation of goals and conditions of activity, self-regulation of the individual in conditions associated with overcoming educational and professional difficulties, based on the adequacy of self-esteem.

4. Professional and social component (civic orientation), which involves the development of a normative, ethical, legal and ethical culture: the education of moral and political beliefs and

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feelings that determine professional and personal behavior. Formation of professional role function based on personal and professional goals and social values, social adequacy of the teacher's personality; development of ethical standards of behavior in the performance of professional functions; fostering personal and professional responsibility for the implementation of value-oriented interactions and regulation of self-development of students; formation of civil, legal and moral responsibility in the process of professional activity. We have identified the stages and components of the structure of organizational and pedagogical support of the pedagogical model for improving the professional competence of physical education teachers in the process of advanced training.

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